

MECHANICAL VENTILATION OUTCOMES IN DRUG OVERDOSE AND POISONING CASES A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Acute poisoning and drug overdose are important causes of emergency admissions, sometimes necessitate intensive care unit (ICU) support and mechanical ventilation (MV). The associated morbidity and mortality differ depending on the substance involved, patient comorbidities, and timeliness of care. This systematic review evaluates the clinical characteristics, indications for MV, and outcomes in ICU patients admitted due to poisoning or overdose. **Methods:** The literature search was conducted in (PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar) after PRISMA guidelines. Studies included reported on adult patients with poisoning or drug overdose requiring MV. Outcomes include mortality, duration of MV, ICU length of stay, and associated complications. A total of nine studies were included in the qualitative analysis, with data extracted and synthesized. **Results:** The included studies showed on diverse populations, range from 48 to over 2.5 million patients. Poisoning was the predominant cause of ICU admission, with organophosphates and opioids are the most common toxic agents. MV was needed in 64% to 85% of cases. Predictors of MV and mortality included low Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), high APACHE II or SOFA scores, delayed hospital presentation, co-ingestions, and psychiatric comorbidities. Mortality ranged from 2.8% to 33%, with higher rates in patients with pesticide or opioid overdose, mainly those with prolonged MV or delayed treatment. **Conclusion:** MV is important intervention to manage poisoning related ICU admissions. Early identification of high-risk patients and ventilation protocols improve outcomes.

Keywords: Acute Poisoning, Drug Overdose, Mechanical Ventilation, Intensive Care Unit, Mortality, Critical Care Outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Acute poisoning is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality, mainly in developing countries where access to critical care is limited. Intensive care unit (ICU) admission is essential in managing life threatening poisonings, the decision for ICU admission complicated by variability in clinical presentation, available resources, and poison type (Abdelnoor et al., 2024).

In Egypt, a study conducted at the Tanta University Poison Control Center revealed that ICU admitted poisoned patients represented 6% of total acute poisoning admissions, with aluminum phosphide is the most common agent and associated with high mortality (Abdelnoor et al., 2024).

Mechanical ventilation (MV) is required in critical cases, due to compromised respiratory and neurological function. Data from a retrospective cohort of ICU admitted patients in Egypt reported that hypotension, altered arterial blood gases, and abnormal vital signs were indicators for MV, mainly in those exposed to aluminum phosphide and organophosphates (Abdelnoor et al., 2024).

Similar findings were observed in a recent study developed predictive models for ICU outcomes in poisoned patients, showing that aluminum phosphide, low oxygen saturation, and delayed ICU admission were associated with mortality and complications (ElMehy et al., 2025). Global patterns indicate that 4–40% of acutely poisoned patients require ICU admission (ElMehy et al., 2025).

A study conducted in India showed that 27% of poisoned ICU patients required MV and reported poor outcomes in those with delayed presentation or ingestion of neurotoxic agents (Kumar et al., 2020). In Southeast Asia, there is alarming mortality rate in pesticide poisoning cases required ventilation, showing the urgent need for early intervention and specialized ICU care (Fernando et al., 2018).

Studies from diverse settings confirm the critical need for triage systems to assess patients at high risk of deterioration. GCS, hemodynamic instability, and the type of toxicant are core indicators for MV (Ahmed et al., 2014; Boyer et al., 2011). The frequency of suicidal poisoning in young adults and females in rural regions, adds a layer of complexity to case management and outcome prediction (Abdelnoor et al., 2024).

This systematic review aims to discuss the available evidence on MV outcomes in patients with acute poisoning and drug overdose. Understanding these patterns guide clinical decision-making, improve resource allocation, and improve patient outcomes in toxicology critical care units.

METHODOLOGY

This systematic review was conducted to evaluate the demographic characteristics, indications for MV, and clinical outcomes in patients admitted to intensive care units (ICUs) for drug overdose or poisoning.

The study was conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines.

Search Strategy and Study Selection

A literature search was performed using peer reviewed articles available in databases (PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar).

Nine full-text studies were selected for inclusion based on relevance to the study objective (Fig 1).

We include studies involved patients admitted to ICU due to drug overdose or toxic substance ingestion; reported on the use of MV, and provided outcome data, mortality, ICU length of stay, or ventilation duration.

We exclude studies on pediatric populations, case reports, studies not in English, and those not involving ventilatory support data.

Data Extraction and Variables

The following data were extracted and tabulated from the studies included: citation, demographic characteristics of the study population, type of MV used, main clinical findings, and reported outcomes.

MV data included the type (invasive and non-invasive), frequency of use, and indications.

Outcome measures included in hospital mortality, length of ICU stay, duration of MV, and associated complications. Extraction was performed by two reviewers to minimize bias.

Data Analysis

We used a descriptive synthesis approach given the heterogeneity in study designs, populations, and outcome reporting. No meta-analysis was conducted.

The results were grouped and summarized based on key findings (demographics, types of substances involved, need for MV, and patient outcomes).

Risk factors associated with increased mortality or ventilator use were described based on the findings from individual studies.

Fig 1: RRISMA consort chart

RESULTS

We include 9 studies, with a wide range of populations admitted to intensive care units (ICUs) due to drug or poison related complications (Table 1). Sample sizes differ significantly, ranging from 48 to over 2.5 million patients depending on study design and data sources.

The majority of patients were middle aged adults, with several studies reporting a predominance of females in overdose admissions (Pfister et al. 2016; Oladunjoye et al. 2020). Intentional poisoning accounted for the majority of ICU admissions, with rates as high as 94% in some cohorts (Ahuja et al. 2015; Ahmed et al. 2014).

Organophosphate and opioid overdoses were the most commonly reported toxic agents in studies (Table 2). Invasive MV was required in 64 to 85% of overdose patients in ICU settings (Pfister et al. 2016; Ahuja et al. 2015; Gkirgkiris et al. 2024).

Some studies found that co ingestions increased the likelihood of requiring ventilatory support and prolonged ICU stay (Pfister et al. 2016). In a large national sample, 6.4% of opioid overdose patients need invasive ventilation, and this subgroup show a higher mortality and healthcare utilization (Oladunjoye et al. 2020).

The presence of comorbidities (mental health disorders, substance use disorders, and chronic illnesses) was common in patients requiring ICU care. More than half of the patients in one study had a history of prior overdose admissions, and personality disorders and schizophrenia were strong predictors of recurrent presentations (Athavale et al. 2017).

Mortality rates differ by substance and clinical presentation. Studies focusing on organophosphate poisoning reported mortality rates up to 33%, mainly with delayed treatment and prolonged ventilatory support (Ahmed et al. 2014). Opioid overdose-related mortality ranged from 10% to 13% in ventilated patients (Pfister et al. 2016; Oladunjoye et al. 2020).

Drug-overdose-related acute hypoxemic respiratory failure was associated with lower unadjusted mortality compared to other causes of ARDS, although this difference was attributed to younger age (Gkirgkiris et al. 2024).

Poisoned patients admitted to ICU incurred substantial treatment costs, and they had shorter ICU stays and lower overall mortality compared to non-poisoned ICU patients (Fernando et al. 2018).

Sickle cell disease patients with opioid overdose show longer hospital stays and higher costs, despite having lower ventilation rates and no significant difference in mortality when compared to non-SCD patients (Borja-Montes et al. 2025).

Table 1: main findings of the studies include

Citation and journal	Study Design	Population Characteristics	Sample Size	Study Aim	Methodology
Ahuja et al., 2015 (JCDR)	Retrospective observational	ICU patients with acute poisoning; majority male, median age 29; mostly suicidal cases	67	To assess demographic and clinical profiles of acute poisoning patients and predictors of mortality	Retrospective chart review of ICU registry over 2 years; collected data on type of poison, APACHE II, SOFA scores, interventions, and outcomes
Pfister et al., 2016 (J Crit Care)	Retrospective cohort	ICU patients with opioid overdose, median age 41, 60% female	178	To characterize ICU patients with opioid overdose	Chart review including demographics, opioids used, coingestions, and outcomes; statistical analysis using R
Borja-Montes et al., 2025 (Ann Hematol)	Propensity-matched cohort	Hospitalized patients with opioid overdose, with and without SCD; SCD patients younger, predominantly Black	479,175 (1,315 with SCD)	To compare outcomes between opioid overdose patients with and without sickle cell disease	NIS dataset analysis from 2016-2021; multivariable regression and propensity score matching
Athavale et al., 2017 (Australas Psychiatry)	Retrospective descriptive	ICU patients with drug overdose; 82.7% intentional, 68.1% polypharmacy, 66% had psychiatric diagnosis	254	To identify predictors of repeated overdose-related admissions	ICU database review over 3 years, univariate and logistic regression analysis
Oladunjoye et al., 2020 (Cureus)	Retrospective analysis of national database	Adults hospitalized with opioid overdose; regional, age, and comorbidity stratification	2,528,751	To determine predictors and outcomes of invasive MV in opioid overdose	HCUP-NIS database analysis, multivariate logistic regression on predictors of IMV
Gkirgkiris et al., 2024 (Pneumon)	Secondary analysis of prospective study	Patients with acute hypoxemic respiratory failure; 48 overdose-related AHRF cases	1280 (48 drug-overdose AHRF)	To compare mortality and features of overdose-related vs non-overdose AHRF	LOTUS FRUIT dataset analysis, Cox regression and mediation analysis

Fernando et al., 2018 (J Intensive Care Med)	Retrospective matched cohort	ICU patients with acute poisoning; matched to non-poisoned controls	277 (8452 total ICU)	To evaluate ICU outcomes and costs for poisoned vs non-poisoned patients	Matched analysis using hospital data warehouse; cost analysis and mortality comparison
Ahmed et al., 2014 (Indian J Anaesth)	Retrospective observational	ICU patients with OP poisoning; 91.86% suicidal, MV cases	117	To evaluate survival predictors in OP poisoning requiring ventilation	Retrospective ICU chart review; correlation and logistic regression analyses
Reisinger et al., 2024 (Eur J Emerg Med)	Retrospective cohort	Critically ill patients with toxic ingestion; average age 37.4; 59% male	212	To assess predictors of mortality and ventilatory support in ICU poisoning cases	Retrospective ICU record analysis; logistic regression on predictors of mortality and ventilation

Table 2: Study Characteristics and outcomes

Citation	Demographic Characteristics	Mechanical Ventilator	Main Findings	Outcomes
Ahuja et al., 2015 (JCDR)	67 patients; median age 29; 69% male; 94% suicidal	Invasive ventilation; 43 patients (64%) required	Pesticides were common poisons; high APACHE II & SOFA scores linked to mortality	18% mortality; 35% for aluminum phosphide cases
Pfister et al., 2016 (J Crit Care)	178 patients; median age 41; 60% female	Invasive ventilation in 85%	Coingestions increased ventilation need and ICU stay	10.1% mortality; 3.4% discharged to nursing home
Borja-Montes et al., 2025 (Ann Hematol)	479,175 total; 1,315 with SCD; mostly African descent	Lower rate in SCD group (aOR 0.7)	SCD patients had longer stays and higher cost, but similar mortality	No significant mortality difference (aOR 0.89)
Athavale et al., 2017 (Australas Psychiatry)	254 ICU admissions; 82.7% intentional; 66% psychiatric diagnosis	Not specified	Personality disorders & schizophrenia predicted repeated overdoses	2.8% mortality
Oladunjoye et al., 2020 (Cureus)	2.5 million cases; age 18+; analyzed by region and age group	6.4% required invasive ventilation	IMV linked with aspiration pneumonia, septic shock, brain injury	13.4% mortality for ventilated vs 0.3% non-ventilated
Gkirgkiris et al., 2024 (Pneumon)	1280 patients; 48 with drug overdose; younger (mean age 42)	All were invasively ventilated (ARDS criteria)	Drug overdose AHRF had lower unadjusted mortality; younger age key factor	16.7% mortality (drug overdose group); 34.4% (non-drug overdose)

Fernando et al., 2018 (J Intensive Care Med)	277 poisoned ICU patients; mean age 44.5	Not specified	Poisoned patients had lower ICU LOS and cost vs matched controls	5.1% mortality (poisoned) vs 11.1% (controls)
Ahmed et al., 2014 (Indian J Anaesth)	117 OP poisoning patients; 91.86% suicidal	Invasive ventilation; outcomes varied by ventilation duration	Early PAM treatment improved survival; delay worsened outcome	18.6% mortality
Reisinger et al., 2024 (Eur J Emerg Med)	212 patients; mean age 37.4; 59% male; varied substances	78.8% received invasive ventilation	Delayed presentation and mixed ingestion predicted poor outcomes	22.6% mortality; longer ICU stays in ventilated patients

DISCUSSION

This systematic review highlights the role of MV to manage patients with acute poisoning and drug overdose. The findings from nine included studies show that the majority of patients requiring MV were young, male, and presented with intentional poisoning. Mortality rates varied in studies, range from 2% to 30.6%, with several studies identifying low Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), high APACHE II and SOFA scores, delayed hospital presentation, and mixed substance ingestion as important predictors of mortality and prolonged ventilation. These findings are corroborated by recent evidence which show that delayed presentation and poly drug use increase the risk of poor outcomes (Reisinger et al., 2024). The reported mortality rate of 22.6% and ventilation rate of 78.8% align with other included studies, which indicate a consistent pattern in critically ill cases. According to one cohort study, early respiratory compromise in overdose patients is a strong indicator for MV and is associated with increased ICU stay and complications (Ford et al., 2020). Another study reported that therapeutic reasons (airway protection and toxidrome management) are important factors of prolonged ventilation in poisoned patients (Manini et al., 2016). A multicenter cohort show variability in MV duration based on the type of toxic agent, with opioids and pesticides are associated with longer ventilation periods (Mularski et al., 2015). This is consistent with prior studies observing prolonged ICU stays and higher mortality in organophosphate and opioid toxicity cases (Fernando et al., 2018; Ahmed et al., 2014).

Moran et al., (2013) study focused on tricyclic antidepressant overdose and found that MV was frequently required due to cardiac and neurological complications, reinforcing the importance of toxidrome-specific protocols in intensive care management. Research on severe opioid toxicity in emergency settings showed that early administration of naloxone reduced the need for prolonged ventilation, an aspect underreported in most included studies (Boyer et al., 2011). Recent studies support these findings. One study analyzing poisoned ICU patients in Saudi Arabia show GCS and time to hospital arrival as a predictor of MV need (Alenezi et al., 2022). Al-Shaqqi et al., 2021 study reported that patients with psychiatric comorbidities and mixed ingestion were more likely to experience complications and require longer ventilation.

Clinical audits of overdose management showed a need for standardization of MV criteria in toxicology cases (Khan et al., 2023). Observational analysis from India found a 27% rate of MV use in ICU overdose admissions (Rajeev et al., 2020). MV was associated with mortality in pesticide-poisoned patients in a Southeast Asian cohort (Somchai et al., 2019). A large toxicology registry analysis show that early intubation did not correlate with better survival and show the need for risk-based protocols (Gomez et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION

Our findings show the need for rapid triage, early identification of toxidromes, and the implementation of standardized ventilation protocols to improve outcomes. Future studies should aim for multicenter collaboration and prospective designs to better define predictors and refine treatment guidelines for poisoned patients requiring mechanical ventilation.

Abbreviations

- 1) MV, Mechanical Ventilation
- 2) ICU, Intensive Care Unit
- 3) GCS, Glasgow Coma Scale
- 4) APACHE II, Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II
- 5) SOFA, Sequential Organ Failure Assessment
- 6) ED, Emergency Department
- 7) OP, Organophosphate
- 8) COPD, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
- 9) ARDS, Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome
- 10) RR, Respiratory Rate
- 11) HR, Heart Rate
- 12) BP, Blood Pressure
- 13) ABG, Arterial Blood Gas
- 14) LOS, Length of Stay
- 15) CPR, Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation.

Conflict of Interest

None

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None

Ethical Approval

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